

Editorial

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WELCOME! We are hereby introducing our new journal, named as “British Journal of Medicine and Medical Research (BJMMR)”

BJMMR is a complete open access, purely online, general medical journal, dedicated to publish medical and medicine research from all disciplines and therapeutic areas. BJMMR is not meant to add just another name in the already populated list of medical journals. In order to synchronize with the very fast paced demand of world medical community, BJMMR is characterized with many unique concepts and policies. BJMMR is a combination of many great peculiarities as the eternal free access, world wide indexation, fast appearance, wide area of fields covered, top class Reviewers engaged, international outreach with no bias to the developed or developing countries representatives, etc. We respect the truth that “Change is the only Constant”. We promise to all medical community that for the sake of science, for providing better service to authors and readers, we will change/evolve our policies with a justified logic. Please be sure that “We are not ‘Constant’, we are changing and changing for YOU”.

Our publishing procedures are bolstered by state-of-the-art ‘RUNNING ISSUE’ concept - which gives the benefit of ‘ZERO WAITING TIME’ for officially accepted papers. Authors have not to wait for next forthcoming issue to get their officially accepted manuscript to be published. We understand that many times it becomes very painful for the authors to wait to see the published version of their paper, even though it has been accepted long time back.

BJMMR will not only publish traditional full research reports, including short communications, but also this journal will publish reports/articles on all stages of the research process like study protocols, pilot studies and pre-protocols. BJMMR is novelty attracting, open minded, peer-reviewed medical periodical, designed to serve as a perfectly new platform for both mainstream and "new ground shaking" works as long as they are technically correct and scientifically motivated.

As a part of social responsibility to promote 'young scientists' (like PhD students, post doctoral students, etc), BJMMR is dedicated to extend all possible helping hand. It is the promise of 'team-BJMMR' that any technical/financial constrain will not be a limitation for any excellent paper to be published in BJMMR. I hope many uniquely designed policies of BJMMR, like "RUNNING ISSUE", etc. will be handy for the 'Young Scientist' community.

As a part of our promise to provide best service to medical community, we have introduced state-of-the-art "SUBCENTRAL" platform, where starting from manuscript submission, manuscript number generation, peer review, revision, payment, invoicing, publication, etc formalities are automated. Hope all these initiatives will open 24X7 service window as well as will augment transparent and fast process compared to traditional system. We are also having many other, cutting-edge technologies and policies/awards like "Research Promotion Program for Developing Countries (RP2DC)", "Reviewer Editor Recognition Program (RERP)", and "Established Author Recognition Program (EARP)", "SCIENCEDOMAIN international Excellence Award" etc. I hope that if you keep an attentive eye in our website, you will discover many attractive policies.

In a broad sense the purpose of this journal is: to help a wide variety of institutions to understand, track and better manage their own progress with the progress of world medical community. Many good technical journals already exist in related fields. This is not another technical journal. Instead, BJMMR will provide reviews by recognized experts across the breadth of related issues, perspective pieces and many other services to help the medical community to move forward.

BJMMR tweets you to 'follow us' in coming issues to see many more changes and surprises, waiting for you.

We welcome you.

Prof. D. A. Kuznetsov